

COACING AND SUPERVISION IN THE ARMY STAFF AND COMMAND MILITARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This study analyzes the role of mentor officers in military schools at the Army Staff and Command School (*Seskoad*), which is the highest development school in the Indonesian Army (TNI-AD) established to educate mid-ranking officers of the TNI-AD and representatives from the Navy (TNI-AL), Air Force (TNI-AU), Indonesian National Police, and friendly foreign countries. The findings of this research highlight the crucial role of mentor officers, emphasizing the need for adequate capabilities and competencies in both military and general knowledge. The contribution of this research can serve as a reference for the management of mentor officer quality as companions to officer students during their education at the Army Staff and Command School (SESKOAD).

Keywords: Mentor Officer, Counseling, Educational and SESKOAD Experience.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources involved in both structural and non-structural organizations must have competencies that align with the roles and needs of the organization. Lyle & Spencer (1993) define competency as an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to criterion-referenced effective and/or superior performance in a job situation. This is necessary to fulfil the organization's vision and mission effectively and efficiently, supporting the concept of the right person in the right place. According to Rivai (2003), competence refers to skills and abilities, and the root word, competent, means capable and skilled. Competence refers to the attributes/characteristics of an individual that make them successful in their work.

The Army Staff and Command School of the Indonesian Army (*Seskoad*) is the central executive body at the Indonesian Army Headquarters directly under the Chief of Staff of the Army (*Kasad*), with the main task of conducting the highest general development of the Indonesian Army and strategic studies to support the tasks of the Indonesian Army. *Seskoad*, as an educational institution, has a vision: the best, respected, and respected. Therefore, this educational institution prioritizes the quality of the participants' results that align with the educational goals. The education aims to prepare leaders of the Indonesian Army and the Indonesian Armed Forces in general, with good personalities and knowledge. The goal of *Seskoad* is to play a role in developing the skills or abilities of officer students from the Seskoad Education Program who have the behavior of a *Sapta Marga* warrior, with knowledge and skills that include knowledge and mastery of tactics and operations and have a physically fit body. Officer students are trained to assume command and staff positions with military

competence, a mixture of knowledge, skills, abilities, motivation, beliefs, values, and interests (Fleishman, Wetrogen, Uhlman, & MarshallMies, 1995)

Previous research tends to focus on the role of lecturers serving at *Seskoad* as seen in research conducted by Kusnowo (2010). The preparation (recruitment) of educational staff at *Seskoad* must be selective and careful as it is a crucial step that needs to be planned in an integrated and continuous manner, meeting general and specific requirements as educational staff, not solely based on appointments but through a Fit and Proper Test involving *Seskoad* as the using unit. Research by Widodo, A.C. (2022) states that the Army Staff and Command School (*Seskoad*) is the highest general development education institution of the Indonesian Army, established to provide knowledge and skills to TNI-AD officers to become leaders. Besides producing military commanders, *Seskoad* also produces alumni who successfully become civilian leaders, even national leaders, and world figures. It is customary in the military world of any country to build a strong and modern armed force. Therefore, an educational institution with staff and command training capabilities is needed.

In promoting the improvement of the abilities and competencies of mentor officers, there are challenges due to the turnover of personnel based on the policy of the Chief of Staff of the Army, considering the general needs of the Indonesian Army. This research aims to analyse future challenges for *Seskoad* as the highest school in the Indonesian Army and a military school whose graduates will have a degree equivalent to an S2 in Land Operations. The focus of this research is to analyse the role of mentor officers in the military school of the Army Staff and Command School in dealing with varying capabilities of officer students in terms of education and assignment experience.

Research Method and Design

In this study, the authors employ a qualitative method, utilizing interview strategies with informants and a case study approach. Through these approaches, facts can be obtained through a question-and-answer process and observations of the teaching and planning processes of existing or prospective instructors at *Seskoad*. This strategy was chosen in alignment with the research objective, which is to qualify instructors at the *Seskoad* military school. According to Creswell (2010), descriptive research is defined as research conducted to determine the values of independent variables, either one or more (independent), without making comparisons or linking one variable to another. Therefore, it can be inferred that the descriptive qualitative method aims to explain the problem in detail and depth. This research uses the concept of Human Resource Planning benefits. Walker (1990) states that, like most organizational practices, the effectiveness of Human Resources planning depends on the perspective in which it is used. Therefore, Human Resources planning needs to have clear and precise goals in mind to carry out the Human Resources planning process more effectively. Additionally, Mondy & Noe (1995) define HR Planning as a systematic process that systematically examines the state of HR to ensure that the right quantity and quality of skills are available when needed.

Data Collection Techniques

This study involves conducting field observations by visiting the Army Staff and Command School (*Seskoad*) and obtaining data from field notes. The study also conducts face-to-face interviews with decision-makers at SESKOAD as informants, and also obtaining data for use in evaluation and educational curriculum.

Data Analysis Technique

This study involves a data analysis process, including qualitative descriptive analysis and interactive analysis (Miles, M. B. et al., 2014), which includes research data collection, data identification, research data reduction related to the research topic, data verification, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Seskoad's Role in Educating Middle Officers of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD) is the embodiment of a harmonious combination of personnel and equipment elements. While both elements need to be in good condition to produce the required defence capabilities for the country, personnel are more critical as they use and control material elements. To ensure the high quality of personnel, educational development plays a crucial role. Education, in this context, refers to all efforts made to convey information, transfer skills to personnel, and train them to be truly capable and ready to perform all necessary tasks. This includes shaping appropriate thinking and emotional responses as military members, resulting in the required mental and physical strength for making the military strong and effective. This encompasses moral strength and resilience, competency, and willingness to act using equipment and weapons appropriately, as well as exercising leadership to achieve organizational goals (Rachman, A., 2020; Widodo, A. C., 2022; Suhandi, C. et al., 2019).

In a broader vision, HR planning consists of estimating HR needs, assessing available HR, and/or matching available HR with requirements (Bartholomew, 1971; Samwel, 2018; Torrington et al., 2004). In a military context, Wang (2005) states in his review paper that effective military HR planning means "continuously having enough people with the necessary competencies to provide the capabilities required by the Government at an affordable cost." A military organization consists of a strict hierarchy structure of positions occupied by soldiers (Jaquette et al., 1977).

Educational staff in the TNI AD environment, based on the Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number KEP/686/IX/2015 dated September 18, 2015, on technical instructions for educational staff, play roles as: 1. facilitators, preparing and presenting sources of knowledge and skills as needed. 2. communicators, transforming knowledge to students. 3. innovators, actively participating in the development and renewal of the teaching and learning process. 4. dynamizers, activating and developing students' learning motivation. 5. evaluators, evaluating students' learning outcomes, developing evaluation techniques, and evaluating the achievement of learning objectives in cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. 6. trainers, providing

and developing skills or physical fitness abilities for students. 7. mentors and caregivers, assisting in solving problems faced by students.

Indonesian Law Number 20 of 2003 on the National Education System, Article 1, regarding general provisions item 6, defines educators as educational personnel qualified as teachers, lecturers, counselors, learning supervisors, educational trainers, tutors, instructors, facilitators, and other designations according to their specialization.

Mentor Officer

A Mentor Officer (*Patun*) is a mid-ranking officer in the IV group tasked with guiding, directing, providing guidance to *Sesko* cadets in academic and non-academic fields, discussions, counseling, personality development, providing solutions, and solving problems faced by cadets and their groups, both in educational materials and other issues inside and outside class hours. *Patun* also has responsibilities in the guidance, care, and assessment processes, including aspects of cadet attitudes and behaviors during education at *SESKOAD*. In general, *Patun* has a role similar to a counselor, supervisor, or facilitator, where their main task is to provide guidance, direction, guidance, and care to students to develop their potential, empower students in problem-solving and decision-making, and improve the quality of students' lives in terms of personality and community involvement. Therefore, a *Patun* should have undergone education at the *Sesko* level and preferably at a higher level, such as the Indonesian Armed Forces Staff and Command School (*Sesko TNI*).

Table 1: Number of *Sesko* Mentor Officers 2021

No	Military Rank	Sesko TNI	Level of Education		
			Magister	Bachelor	High School
1	Colonel	3	10	4	6

Table 2: Number of *Sesko* Mentor Officers 2022

No	Military Rank	Sesko TNI	Level of Education		
			Magister	Bachelor	High School
1	Colonel	5	2	8	6

Academically, a Mentor Officer should also have high qualifications. With a high educational qualification, a Mentor Officer will find it easier to provide counselling and guidance to develop the potential of officer cadets. Additionally, with a high educational qualification, a mentor will find it easier to encourage and assist cadets in discussions and provide perspectives in problem-solving, both in academic and general life.

According to Zwell (2007), the five competency categories are task achievement, relationship, personal attributes, managerial, and leadership. 1. Task achievement is competency related to performance, including outcome-based orientation, performance management, influence, initiative, effectiveness, efficiency in production, flexibility, innovation, quality, continuous improvement, and technical skills. 2. Relationship is a competency category related to communication and working patterns with other individuals in the organization. Relationship competencies include cooperation, service-oriented orientation, concern, organizational

intelligence, relationship building, conflict resolution, communication, and cross-cultural sensitivity. 3. Personal attributes are intrinsic competencies of individuals and relate to how people think, learn, and develop. Personal attributes include integrity and honesty, self-development, firmness, decision quality, stress management, analytical thinking, and conceptual thinking. 4. Managerial competencies are related to management, supervision, and development. Managerial competencies include motivating, empowering, and developing others. 5. Leadership competencies are related to leading an organization to achieve organizational goals, vision, and purposes. Leadership competencies include visionary leadership, strategic thinking, entrepreneurial orientation, change management, building organizational commitment, building focus and purpose, fundamentals, and values.

According to Lyle & Spencer (1993), competencies have underlying characteristics. Underlying characteristics are parts of a person's personality that are embedded and inherent, often reflected in various task-related situations. The underlying characteristics according to Lyle & Spencer (1993) include: In every individual's personality, there are several underlying characteristics of competency, including: 1. Motive is consistency in thinking about something desired, leading to an event. According to Spencer, motive is behavior such as controlling, directing, guiding, choosing to face certain events, or achieving specific goals. 2. Trait is a characteristic that appears both physically and behaviourally in someone, emerging as a response to specific information, situations, and conditions. 3. Self-concept is an individual's attitude, values, or imagination in viewing and acting in specific situations and conditions. 4. Knowledge is an individual's understanding of known and consciously realized information within a specific scope. This competency characteristic can be seen from various perspectives, including education, test values, and learned and developed understanding. 5. Skill. Skill is the culmination of the previous four characteristics. Skill is a person's ability to perform tasks, both physically and mentally, in specific areas. Skills are acquired through motives, traits, self-concept, and good knowledge. Someone who possesses these five characteristics undoubtedly has competent skills.

A hierarchical skill development scheme is proposed for fundamental non-technical skills in a military context (Cavaleiro et al., 2022). Military personnel have been proven to play a crucial role in whether candidates stay or leave military service (Ibrahim et al., 2021) in actual military command and control, both in doctrine and practice (Burke, 2018). The role and situation of women in military service are a specific topic. The well-being of women in the military is influenced by many different factors, such as career, family life, individual characteristics, military events and obligations, and resources (Segal and Lane, 2016).

To conduct HR planning for military organizations, specificity must be determined. Wang (2005) states that the military workforce system is characterized by its closed nature and strict hierarchy, recruiting only at the lowest rank and filling all higher-ranking vacancies through internal promotion. Each recruit must undergo training before being ready to perform any tasks in the organization (Hall & Fu, 2015). Furthermore, Wang (2005) states in his review paper that effective military HR planning means "continuously having enough people with the necessary competencies to provide the capabilities required by the Government at an affordable

cost." A military organization consists of a strict hierarchy structure of positions occupied by soldiers (Jaquette et al., 1977).

Human resources are based on their military ranks, and the distribution of HR lists the number of personnel for different groups according to specific classifications (Guerry & De Feyter, 2009). Facing the rapidly advancing developments in science, based on interviews with the Corps Commander with the authors stating that:

"""" Seskoad has taken advanced steps by preparing educators/mentors who have undergone Sesko TNI education and equivalent general education at the Magister level, where I, as the Corps Commander, expect that teaching and mentoring can proceed as expected."

The implementation of enhancing the competence of mentor officers by participating in military education according to their ranks and general education to support their main duties.

Based on the Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number Kep/97a/X/2019 dated December 23, 2020, regarding the regular education curriculum of the Army Staff and Command School (*Seskoad*), mentor officers carry out guidance and mentoring with the following method:

1. Objectives. The purpose of guidance and mentoring is to assist cadets in completing/following the teaching and learning process, especially for cadets experiencing learning difficulties/behavioral, academic, and physical problems so that educational goals can be maximally achieved.
2. Targets of Guidance and Mentoring.
 - a. Achieving the consolidation of attitudes and behaviors as soldiers that follows Pancasila, Sapta Marga, and the Oath of the Soldier.
 - b. Achieving mastery of knowledge and skills, including social and technological knowledge, doctrine and warfare, management, strategic issues, territorial, operational and war exercises at the tactical and operational levels.
 - c. Achieving the formation of good body conditions, maintaining physical fitness, and agility.
3. Methods and Techniques. Guidance and mentoring are aimed at providing additional material in accordance with the Basic Three Patterns of Army Education. The techniques/methods of guidance and mentoring are as follows:
 - a. The methods used are persuasive, stimulative, suggestive, educative, and instructive according to the situation, conditions, and cadet developments.
 - b. The techniques used include:
 - 1) Direct guidance and mentoring.
 - 2) Indirect guidance and mentoring.

- 3) Exemplification.
 - 4) Habituations.
 - 5) Group discussions.
 - 6) Activities in Student organizations
4. Stages of Preparation and Time. The use of time in guidance and mentoring is by utilizing spare time, rest hours, and mentoring hours.
 5. Evaluation. The evaluation of guidance and mentoring must be carried out periodically every month to identify existing shortcomings and at the same time consolidate steps for guidance and mentoring activities in the following month, aiming for therapeutic purposes and ensuring the objectivity of the assessment.

The profession of a mentor officer is a job that requires adequate abilities, both military and general abilities, and also understanding teacher concepts and approaches (Kember and Kwan 2002) and their approaches to learning (e.g., Gow and Kember 1993; Kember and Gow 1994; Martin and Balla 1991; Richardson 2005; Samuelowicz and Bain 1992; Prosser and Trigwell 1999), or more generally with the context of student learning quality (Kember 1997).

The competence of a mentor officer in carrying out education at Seskoad is something that must be the basis for supervising officer students. According to Miller, Rankin, and Neathey (2001), competence is a description of what someone needs to know or do to perform their job well.

Speaking of professional competence means talking about how a mentor officer can provide learning services to their students. Because professional competence is the ability to master the learning material extensively and deeply, connecting the content of learning materials by utilizing communication and information technology and providing guidance to students in accordance with national education standards. Therefore, mentor officers are required to have broad insights and mastery of theoretical concepts, capable of choosing the right models, strategies, and methods in carrying out learning activities.

According to Boytatzis (1982), competence is the capacity in a person that enables them to meet the requirements of a job in an organization so that the organization can achieve the expected results. Professionalism of mentor officers is built through the mastery of competencies, which is also necessary in completing their work in providing guidance to officer students. According to Wood, Wallace, and Zeffane (2001), Robbins and Judge (2007), and Harris (2000) as quoted in Marliana Budhiningtyas W (2011), it is explained that the concept of competence as a combination of talent (attitude) and ability. Talent indicates the capability to learn something, it is potential. While ability refers to an individual's capacity to perform various tasks in a job.

Furthermore, Fogg (2004:90) divides competence into 2 (two) categories, namely basic competencies and differentiating competencies based on the criteria used to predict job performance. Basic competencies (Threshold competencies) are the main characteristics,

usually basic knowledge or skills such as the ability to read, while differentiating competencies are competencies that make someone different from others.

Continuous planning for the competence of mentor officers will produce competent officer students who are ready to carry out their duties. Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that competence is an individual's ability to complete their tasks both individually and in groups to improve the abilities of officer students.

Counselling

The terms guidance and counselling have become very popular today, even playing a crucial role in our education system. This is evident because Guidance and Counselling have been included in our educational curriculum. Guidance and counselling play an increasingly important role in improving human resources and developing the personality and potential (talents, interests, and abilities) of students.

The ability of a guiding officer (Mentor) involves different abilities and styles in conducting counselling for *Seskoad* officers, so adequate abilities are required from the Mentor. School counsellors need to be professional practitioners of competent culture (Holcomb-McCoy & Chen-Hayes, 2011). The American School Counsellor Association's (ASCA) position statement on cultural diversity emphasizes that school counsellors must work for the success of all students from all cultures (ASCA, 2009). Overall, school counsellors should work to develop self-awareness, knowledge, and skills when working with students from different cultures (Remley & Herlihy, 2014).

While other cultures have been explored in-depth in the professional school counselling literature (Bradley, Johnson, Rawls, & Dodson-Sims, 2005; Byrd & Hays, 2012; Smith-Adcock, Daniels, Lee, Villalba, & Indelicato, 2006; Yeh, 2001), military culture is often foreign to educators who frequently encounter military students and their families (Atuel, Esqueda, & Jacobson, 2011). Every school district in the United States has children who are in some way connected to the military, and 80% of all military children attend public schools (Military Child Education Coalition, 2014). Therefore, it is crucial for school counsellor's to have knowledge in navigating military culture to support military students and their family members in their schools (Luby, 2012; US Department of Veterans Affairs, 2014).

Hierarchy is another important aspect that is apparent at the surface-level culture of the military community. Rank and order are rigid in the military, with military members expected to show respect and obedience to their superiors (Martins & Lopes, 2012). This authoritarian structure can also be mirrored in military family life (Hall, 2008). Overall, the rank of service members determines how much is earned financially (Huebner, 2013; Luby, 2012), how much education is provided, the level of access to resources (Hall, 2008), and the expected amount of responsibility (US Department of Defence, 2014). The rank of service members affects the identity and feelings of family members, as families identify their position in the military community (Drummet, Coleman, & Cable, 2003). School counsellors must be aware that rank can affect not only the family's economic level but also their stress level, as it can determine the duration and frequency of service member placements (Luby, 2012).

According to Palmer and McMahon (2000) cited by McLeod (2004), counselling is not only an individual learning process but also a social activity that has social meaning. People often use counselling services at points of transition, such as from childhood to adulthood, marriage to divorce, the desire for treatment, and others. Counselling is also a cultural agreement in the sense of a way to cultivate the ability to adapt to social institutions.

Furthermore, according to Shertzer and Stone (1980), counselling is an effort to help individuals through a personal interaction process between the counsellor and the counselee so that the counselee can understand themselves and their environment, make decisions, and set goals based on their beliefs, making the counselee feel happy and effectively behave.

Based on the decision of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number Kep/46/I/2022 regarding the regular education curriculum of the Army Staff and Command School of the Indonesian Army. Mentors are tasked with carrying out guidance and nurturing with the Guidance and Nurturing Method with the following directives:

1. Guidance and nurturing are directed towards achieving attitudes and behaviours, mastery of knowledge and skills, and physical abilities to support the smooth running of the teaching and learning process during education. The methods and techniques of guidance and nurturing used are as follows:
 - a. The methods used are persuasive, stimulative, suggestive, educative, and instructive according to the situation and the development conditions of Officer Students.
 - b. The techniques used include exemplification, group discussions, counselling, remedial teaching, and sociometry.
2. The goals of guidance and nurturing activities are to support the achievement of educational goals for Officer Students as a whole.
3. Targets.
 - a. In the field of attitudes and behaviours. Achieving attitudes and behaviours of Officer Students as TNI AD soldiers with *Sapta Marga* spirit and adhering to the Soldiers Oath.
 - b. In the field of knowledge and skills. Achieving knowledge and skills more determined to support the implementation of duties as Middle Rank Officers Gol V/Letkol in TNI AD subordinate units.

Willis (2014: 18) defines counselling as an assistance effort provided by a trained and experienced counsellor to individuals who need it, so that individuals can develop their potential optimally, cope with their problems, and adapt to a constantly changing environment. Results of an interview with the Deputy Commander of *Seskoad*, showed that *Seskoad* has continuously conducted studies to provide advice and input to the Chief of Staff about educators who will be placed in *Seskoad*, ideally for educational levels, they must be at least Magisters, and if possible, Doctors.

Tabel 3: The Curriculum Differences of the *Seskoad*, US Army, and Australian Army

No	Seskoad
1	Having values and character to influence people in the work environment with the principles of struggle based on Pancasila, Sapta Marga, Soldiers Oath, and the Eight Obligations of the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI) through the implementation of managerial abilities for problem-solving and critical thinking in decision-making within its authority and as administrative staff to provide advice in accordance with the duties of the V group position both within and outside the structure of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD).
2	Mastering the theory and practice as a training organizer in the field of tactics and techniques according to the V group position both within and outside the structure of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD).
3	Able to analyze each problem, threat, defense strategy of the land territory, and strategic environmental developments as a basis for advice, input, and considerations in decision-making in the V group position both within and outside the structure of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD).
4	Capable of producing written works and discoveries with new ideas/concepts in the field of science and technology as well as the military in the V group position both within and outside the structure of the Indonesian Army (TNI AD).
	US Army (CGSOC)
1	Enhancing the understanding of selected mid-level officers as potential leaders so that they possess analytical, critical, and creative thinking within the framework of Unified Land Operations (ULO).
2	Conducting various operations. Enhancing understanding of the concepts of Large Scale Combat Operations (LSCO).
3	Implementation of operational concepts seen from strategic, operational, and tactical levels.
	Australian Army (ASDC)
1	The education target is to prepare officers who can apply the taught material, including strategy, war history, Australian policy, leadership theory, and Joint Operation Planning, to the duties as unit commanders or staff in a multi-domain and government institution environment.
2	The education curriculum used at ACSC 2022 is tailored to the Joint Professional Military Education (JPME) program, which includes the development of international standard military personnel professionalism by combining the PSC(J) curriculum and the Master of Military and Defence Studies from ANU. The focus and priority of education at ACSC are to produce outputs with PSC(J) qualifications, including capabilities in the military and academic fields. The aspects of military professionalism development provided at ACSC 2022 include joint operational warfighting (JOP module), capability and futures studies (Capability and ATF modules), and personal development through the Command, Leadership, and Ethics (CLE module). The material for the development of military professionalism is aligned with the material for the development of academic capabilities at the post-graduate level with a focus on the Military and Defence Studies Program (MDSP) from ANU, divided into 6 modules: Strategy, Operations 1, Operations 2, Leadership Theory (part of the CLE module, ASE, and ASDP.)

Assessment and evaluation of educational outcomes serve as the basis for determining future educational plans. Considering the existing understanding, it can be concluded that Counseling is an ability to assist an individual in improving their capabilities, enabling officer cadets to fulfill their tasks during the implementation of education.

Professional Educational Institution Service Experience

A profession is a job or activity carried out by an individual that serves as a source of livelihood, requiring expertise, skills, or abilities that meet certain quality standards or norms and necessitate professional education. Experience is used to refer to knowledge and skills about

something acquired through involvement or association with it over a certain period. In general, experience refers to knowing how, or procedural knowledge, rather than propositional knowledge. Knowledge based on experience is also known as empirical knowledge or posteriori knowledge. Someone with considerable experience in a specific field is called an expert. According to Foster (2015:40), work experience is a measure of the time or duration a person has spent in understanding the tasks of a job and has performed well.

Experience is an integral part of daily human life. Experience is highly valuable to every individual and can be given to anyone for use as guidance and human learning. According to Pine II and Gilmore (1999:12), experience is an event that happens and binds to each individual personally. According to Kotler (2005:217), experience is a learning process that influences a person's behaviour change. A Mentor Officers' work period with the positions ever held can be measured from the start of their work (teaching) and counselling until the end of their duty period in performing their duties, and this is because of transfers between units and retirement. According to Fuller (1969:13), someone skilled in improving and enhancing the teaching and learning process is required to have knowledge and skills in the teaching and learning process and possess a diploma relevant to their duties.

The teaching profession and the lecturer profession are special fields of work carried out based on the following principles:

1. Having talent, interest, a calling, and idealism.
2. Commitment to improving the quality of education, faith, piety, and noble character.
3. Academic qualifications and educational background appropriate to the job.
4. Possessing the required competencies according to the job.
5. Having responsibility for the implementation of professional duties.

The competency of educational personnel, in this case, the patun, can be influenced by several internal and external factors. According to Sutermeister (1976), internal factors are those related to the individual, including education, experience, and work ethic. External factors, or situational factors, encompass the climate, work environment, facilities and infrastructure, and social environment.

According to Foster (2015:56), work experience indicators include:

- a. Length of time/work period: A measure of the time or duration a person has spent so that they can understand the tasks of a job and have performed well.
- b. Level of knowledge and skills possessed: Knowledge refers to concepts, principles, procedures, policies, or other information needed by employees. Knowledge also includes the ability to understand and apply information to job responsibilities.

Furthermore, according to Fubrin (in Mangkunegara, 2013:77), Career Development is an employee activity that helps employees plan their future careers in the company so that both the company and the employees can develop themselves well. Additionally, according to

Dewey (2012:147), experience does not refer to something currently happening but rather to something ongoing in the inner life that can be achieved through intuition and reason.

Past experience is often a benchmark for a lecturer in carrying out their duties. This experience includes the time when they were led by other program heads or when they led a program or another organization. Johnson (2007:18) further states that experience brings out a person's potential, and this potential gradually emerges over time in response to various experiences.

Work enthusiasm is one of the supporting factors for a *patun* in carrying out their activities. According to Leightemy in Nitisemito (2010:160), something positive and good can contribute to work in a better sense. Furthermore, William and Keith Davis (2003:130) define work enthusiasm as an individual's attitude toward their work environment and their availability and cooperation with others as a whole according to their best abilities for the company's benefit.

In the military and corporate environments, an employee with work experience in various fields will provide benefits for their users, enabling them to complete their tasks quickly and effectively. According to Robbins (2006), the work experience possessed by an employee will support the creation of optimal performance. This will be the opposite if an employee lacks work experience; achieving optimal performance will be difficult. Furthermore, Johnson (2007:228) states that experience brings out a person's potential. Full potential emerges gradually over time in response to various experiences.

Table 4: Authority Level and Responsibility for Educator Guidance (Chief of Staff of the Army Decision Number Kep/686/IX/2015 dated 18-9-2015)

ACTIVITIES	FIELDS	ACTORS IN CHARGE	ORGANIZERS	COORDINATORS
PROVISION	SELECTION	MABES TNI AD (Army Headquarters)	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI AD COMMANDER OF THE UNIT, BRANCH COMMANDER, AND THE DIRECTOR OF THE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION FOR EACH BRANCH
	APPOINTMENT	COMMANDER OF THE TNI ARMY CHIEF OF STAFF	MABES TNI (Indonesian National Armed Forces Army Headquarters) MABES TNI AD	
	EXTENSION OF SERVICE PERIOD	COMMANDER OF THE TNI ARMY CHIEF	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY

		OF STAFF		EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
TRAINING	BASIC EDUCATION	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	EXTERNAL AGENCIES
UTILIZATION	CREDIT VALUES	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	
	CAREER DEVELOPMENT	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	PROVISION OF TEACHING FACILITIES	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD
MAINTENANCE	ALLOWANCE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	HONORARIUM	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	POSITIONAL MARK	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	AWARDS	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	BASIC LEAVE	ARMY EDUCATION	ARMY EDUCATION	ARMY EDUCATION AND

		AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	TRAINING INSTITUTE
	ACCOMODATION	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	HEALTH	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
	RECREATION	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE	ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE
SEPERATION	TERMINATION	COMMANDER OF THE TNI ARMY CHIEF OF STAFF	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD	MABES TNI MABES TNI AD ARMY EDUCATION AND TRAINING INSTITUTE

Based on several theories confronted with the regulations in force in the Indonesian Army, the authors believe that the experience of a *Patun* who has a track record of serving and diverse work experiences in various units or educational institutions can influence the guidance provided to officer cadets.

CONCLUSION

The research results indicate that the competence of guidance officers requires specific planning and improvement, especially the placement of guidance officers at *Seskoad* based on the decision of the Chief of Staff of the Army. The need for guidance officers has been proposed step by step to the Army Headquarters, and decisions are based on the results of the job position meeting. Considering the data on competence and qualifications of guidance officers, continuous planning is needed for both military knowledge and general knowledge.

Competence is discussed as the basis for becoming competent in a job where military work is highly segmented. The combination of motives, characteristics, self-concept, attitudes or values, content knowledge or cognitive behaviour skills; individual characteristics are competencies expected by leadership to be possessed by certain individuals or all employees,

which are related to individual competencies needed to complete the tasks of officer cadets. The specific competence of mentor officers with guidance and counselling, especially for specific subjects, allows for determining the essential features of a competent guide. The main idea is the realization by guidance officers of the desired and available outcomes of self-development, which is a specific high-level competence with individual improvement strategies set through the actual conditions of specific competence development, personal abilities, interests, needs; providing continuous development processes by combining various forms of qualification improvement, including formal, non-formal, and informal education. Counseling and guidance programs at the military school, Seskoad, need to focus on competency enhancement and the placement of guidance officers according to the needs of Seskoad.

Competing interests

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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